

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE CURRENT STATE OF E-LEARNING, FUTURE TREND, WAYS TO MAKE IT SOPHISTICATED AND PERFECT, ITS SIGNIFICANCE AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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Abstract

Each country has its own educational system that depends on many factors such as language, culture, stage of development, demographics, and geographic location. These education systems have evolved and developed in accordance with the country's features and, thus, each country has its own unique educational system, though most countries share commonalities directly copied or slightly modified from each other. In the current globalized world, countries exchange experiences and collaborate on research to find better and more sophisticated education systems and implement the most effective ones. Today, people can travel anywhere around the world and, therefore, it is important to follow international teaching norms, creating the opportunity for people to participate in any training regardless of place, time, or distance. With the demands of the current developmental stage of society wherein artificial intelligence, electronic environment, and the fourth and even fifth industrial revolution prevail, it is essential to reconsider even long-held teaching strategies to match the demands of a rapidly changing present and swiftly approaching future.

In recent years, much has been made about various learning methods such as distance learning, online learning, and e-learning. In some cases, we began the initial stages of testing and introducing these new strategies but could only go so far without clear rules and regulations. But the world did not wait. It has been almost two years since the outbreak of the global pandemic, when all countries were forced to stop or reduce traditional classroom teaching and made to implement different forms of teaching such as electronic, distance, and telelearning, not only for elementary and high school students, but even for college and university students! However, it is evident that there are differences in the methods and quality of education, in learning, in grading, in attendance and participation of students, in the ability to learn independently, and in attitudes and evaluations of parents and the public. There are both good and bad aspects to e-learning. Therefore, this article aims to analyze the state of e-learning implemented at Mongolian University of Science and Technology (MUST) and make recommendations.

Keywords: e-learning, education, quality, performance, methods, evaluation, object

Current state: Electronic teaching has been conducted in accordance with the temporary regulations issued by the Education Policy and Regulation Department of MUST from the time when remote teaching began [1,4]. MUST published instructions on its web page, including an "E-learning web" portal where professors and instructors logged in with their usernames and IDs to upload their course files. The files could include lecture slides, lecture notes, lists of main and supplementary textbooks, self-exam questions for each lecture, midterm papers, assignments, etc. Every student can access this portal with his/her own student ID and study the course materials for the classes he/she is enrolled in, as well as communicate with instructors, submit questions, and view the instructors' answers, etc. In general, classes are taught according to a preset schedule wherein those with access to the internet, the necessary equipment, and can view the course online at that preset time, can directly connect with the instructor and attend the lecture online. Additionally, these students can connect with their instructors directly or indirectly at any time. The head of the department and the relevant personnel check the course files of individual instructors every time and make notes on required changes and/or improvements to individual files. Each instructor can track how students learn by accessing the statistical data available on the e-learning website (Table 1). Each instructor is required to report the e-learning progress of their students to their department head

every week, who then compiles all the information and prepares an e-learning report (Table 2). It is further consolidated and reviewed at the level of constituent schools and MUST [1,5].

At the end of the semester, each instructor will award up to 70 points based on students' online assignments, tests, and their level of class participation, and 30 points based on their final exam. The final exam is also carried out according to the pre-given instructions and questions, either by directly answering the questions from the course instructor live at a preset time, or by taking an online test at a scheduled time. This is a general picture of how e-learning is going today. As is to be expected, e-learning has both strengths and weaknesses.

Strengths:

1. It is directed toward modern trends in education.
2. Each instructor's course materials are regularly reviewed, creating an opportunity to improve their content and quality.
3. There is an opportunity to instruct many people at the same time, independent of the capacity of a physical classroom, time, or location.
4. Students can interact with instructors and course files on a regular basis.
5. Results of exams and tests are protected from a certain level of interference.
6. Allows greater flexibility in location for both students and instructors.

Table 1

Check data to monitor how teachers teach their lessons.

№	Name of School	Student ID	Full name	Phone number, email address	Number of access	Total duration of access	Total time of studying	Average time of studying	Study time in a week

Table 2

Check data to monitor how students study their lessons.

№	Code of the course	Title of the course	Credit	Teacher ID	Teacher name	Number of enrolled students	Number of students who accessed in a week	Total time of access in a week	Attendance (%)

Weaknesses:

1. Some students have limited access to an online environment, whether due to lack of internet access or computer hardware.

2. A course file that has not been discussed by the team and does not fully meet the requirements might be posted.

3. It can be hard to track if students communicate with their instructors and access their course materials.

4. Access to the course is expressed only in quantitative terms, which is flawed from the qualitative point of view.

5. Increased ability for students to cheat on examinations and tests.

6. There are not as many proven and tested methods based on scientific research.

If the above-mentioned strengths and shortcomings can be so easily observed after little more than a year of observing e-learning, clearly it is necessary to carry out extensive research and analysis of e-learning issues on a wide scale involving many educational institutions. Scientific evaluation is required.

Quality of education, its components:

The most important outcome of e-learning should be the quality of learning. However, there is still no broad consensus on how to objectively quantify an educational outcome. Based on my forty years of research and experience working in higher education institutions, I believe that, first, we should develop a common understanding of how to evaluate quality levels. During my post-graduate studies at Moscow Mining University in Russia in 1989-1991, I learnt a lot about how to evaluate quality, what the quality evaluation indicators are, and how to select them. Using what I learnt, I earned my Doctor of Technical Science degree by carrying out research in "Assessment of the Quality Level of Mine Excavator Repair and Technical Service Systems" in 1991, and then my Doctor of Science degree on the subject of "Quality Management of Excavator Operations" at the Irkutsk Technical University in 1998. Because of that, I can confidently say that the problem of studying and evaluating the quality of any product, or service has a scientific basis[2,3].

Therefore, we must carefully consider the issues associated with evaluating the quality of education, especially e-learning: where to start, in what order, and how to quantify the quality. From this point of view, quality of teaching depends on quality of course files, which is a unit constituent of the teaching. Therefore, the quality of e-learning should be evaluated in the following order:

1. Rate the quality level of each course file - In other words, if the course file is of high quality, it implies the lesson quality will likewise be high. Now, of course, quality teaching depends not just on course files, but on the instructor and the students. Therefore, we must discover the cause of any quality weaknesses.

2. One of the main factors of quality education is the instructor. Even with a high-quality teaching file, if the instructor delivers the lesson poorly, does not enrich it, is unable to answer students' questions, or is unable or unwilling to have a good relationship with students, student motivation is diminished, leading to poor educational outcomes.

3. Learning environment. The quality of e-learning depends on: (1) the capacity of the technical equipment used by the leading educational stakeholder or instructor, and the environment in which the teacher conducts e-learning, (2) internet, online environment, and hardware of the participating students or the receivers.

We must develop science-based methods to evaluate these components individually.

Theory and method for quantifying teaching quality

Any type of training is a service, and the quality of this service can and should be evaluated by the quality of the outcome, in this case, the quality of a student's learning activity. In other words, the number of qualified graduates out of total graduates, or the number of graduates who are invited to work for certain companies. Evaluating the quality of education is a matter of choosing the correct indicator values for the object to be evaluated and determining the degree to which their values are close to the values of the reference object or basic indicators. Therefore, the selection of basic refer-

ence parameters is the first task to be solved when assessing the quality of any product or service. To assess quality comprehensively, it should always be remembered that when choosing the total number of indicators, you should not choose indicators that are directly related to each other, because such indicators may contain the same information or meaning.

When selecting indicators for quality assessment, an indicator may not be selected if it does not have a significant impact on the outcome. Considering the rest of the indicators as defining indicators, it is necessary to select them as a set or combination of parameters for assessing the quality of work, services, and products. The independence of the parameters used in the comprehensive quality assessment makes it possible to use statistical, probabilistic, and mathematical methods for predicting the quality of products and services, for developing a specific method to evaluate, and for conducting research. The basic parameters for assessing the quality of objects with the same purpose must meet the following requirements:

1. be the best in terms of achieved levels by objects of the same type
2. help identify indicators that will play a key role in improving quality level
3. be able to change and/or evolve as provision of education becomes more sophisticated.

These requirements are met only by the model of the reference object, which consists of the parameters or baselines of such a level as are created for one of the objects of that type. Therefore, a benchmark object model is a mock model consisting of the best performance of various objects for the same purpose. It is more convenient to define the baseline parameters of the reference object model in percentage. Therefore, the percentage (X_{ij}) of parameters (indicators) (P_{ij}) selected to assess the quality of objects with the same purpose is determined by the following expression[2,3]:

$$X_{ij} = \frac{P_{ij}}{Q_i}$$

where i – sequence number of an object, j – sequence number of parameters or indicators, Q_i – main indicator of the i th object. Depending on the quality level of the object to be assessed, a matrix can be created with the parameters selected directly without defining the main indicators and individual indicators. An object can be defined as a specific item, product, or service. As mentioned above, the process of assessing the quality of teaching begins with assessing the quality of course files. Then after determining the values of individual parameters, they are entered into a matrix.

In order to make the method clear, consider the following example: when assessing the quality of a course file for a particular course, the evaluators are either the students or the teachers of the relevant major. These form the rows of the matrix. The scores from the evaluators form the columns of the matrix. In this way, we will be able to individually assess the file quality of all the courses taught by the department. It will then be possible to assess the quality level of all course files. At this point, the rows of the matrix are the subjects. Based on this principle, we can scientifically assess the quality

level of course files, teachers, students, departments, etc., using the method below. If we choose real indicators and not personal metrics to make a quality assessment, then $P_{ij} = X_{ij}$:

$$X_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} X_{11}X_{12} \dots X_{1j} \dots X_{1n} \\ X_{21}X_{22} \dots X_{2j} \dots X_{2n} \\ \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\ X_{i1}X_{i2} \dots X_{ij} \dots X_{in} \\ \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\ X_{m1}X_{m2} \dots X_{mj} \dots X_{mn} \end{pmatrix}$$

The row of the matrix consists of the values of the eigenvalues of the j th parameter belonging to an object, whereas each column indicates the eigenvalue of one of the j th parameters of each object.

From each column of the matrix, the lowest (good) values of the percentage of quality indicators are selected and appropriate indices are assigned:

$$\{X_{cj}\} = \{X_{c1}, X_{c2} \dots X_{cj} \dots X_{cn}\}$$

The combination of base values provides a dynamic (moving) model of the reference object, which contains the best properties represented by the $\{X_{cj}\}$ metrics. If all X_{cj} values belong to the same object, the reference is a real model of the object. However, this is a very rare or almost non-existent case.

Subsequent comparisons are performed by comparing individual measures of quality indicators to baseline measures to other measures. The parameters are selected individually according to their impact on quality. If the opposite, their inverse should be taken. If positive and negative measures are necessarily selected for the quality assessment, the quality indicator is determined by assessing them separately and then finding the average. In this way, selecting the indicators chosen to evaluate the quality level and put them into a matrix form makes assessing the quality level of any product or service easy.

The quality level expressed in units of indicators (q_{ij}) or, in other words, separately for each indicator, is the ratio of the percentage of the basic parameters of the standard object (X_{cj}) to the same parameters of the object number i :

$$q_{ij} = \frac{X_{cj}}{X_{ij}} < 1$$

Quality unit indicators have no units of measurement and for any object they are always less than 1. The lowest (highest) or best indicators (X_{ij}) min, max are selected from the matrix, and (X_{ij}) min, max) = X_{cj} for the reference machine. The X_{ij} value of any machine is close to its X_{cj} value, which means that it is equal to one or close to the best value. Therefore, the level of quality expressed in unit indicators is measured by the following expression for the reference object:

$$q_{cj} = \frac{X_{cj}}{X_{cj}} = 1$$

To determine the comprehensive quality level of the object by the combination of the quality levels expressed by the selected unit indicators, the coefficient indicating the ranking percentage of the quality level expressed by each unit indicator of the i th object must

be determined. Therefore, when there are n parameters, the percentage (ranking) of the quality level expressed by each unit parameter of the object in their sum can be found by the following formula:

$$m_{ij} = \frac{q_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^n q_{ij}}$$

Percentage of quality level expressed per unit indicator for reference (model) objects:

$$m_{ij} = \frac{q_{cj}}{\sum_{j=1}^n q_{cj}} = \frac{1}{n}$$

The coefficient of participation (Y_{ij}) of the quality levels expressed by each unit indicator in the general quality level of the object is determined by the following expression depending on the ranking percentage:

$$Y_{ij} = \frac{1 - m_{ij}}{1 - m_{cj}}$$

The participation coefficient of the quality levels expressed by each unit indicator in the general quality level of the benchmark object is found by the following expression:

$$Y_{cj} = \frac{1 - m_{cj}}{1 - m_{cj}} = 1$$

The value of the sum of the quality levels expressed in unit indicators is determined by the sum of mean square method for the object number i by calculating their participation coefficient (Y_{ij}) using the following formula:

$$\omega_i = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (Y_{ij} q_{ij})^2}$$

Value of the sum of quality levels expressed in unit indicators for reference objects:

$$\omega_c = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (Y_{cj} q_{cj})^2} = \sqrt{n}$$

The general (comprehensive) quality level of the object is equal to the ratio of the sum of the quality levels expressed by the unit indicators of the object to the sum of the quality levels of the reference object or is expressed as follows:

$$K_i = \frac{\omega_i}{\omega_c} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n (Y_{ij} q_{ij})^2}$$

With this methodology, we can not only assess the quality of the files for all courses, the quality level of teachers, and the quality level of all courses taught by the department, but also assess the quality of the course using a comprehensive scientific approach and many other methods can be used. As a result, based on this research, it will be possible to assess the teaching quality of the constituent schools of a specific university and of all national universities. Thus, based on the assessment derived by conducting science-based research, we can determine the current level of education quality, and develop a comprehensive understanding of how to improve the quality of education and prepare qualified staff in a success fostering environment.

Closing section:

Given our country's characteristics, the state of e-learning in the past, the need to improve e-learning in

the future, and e-learning's positive and negative aspects, the following suggestions are presented:

The importance of e-learning and suggestions:

1. Students will have the opportunity to re-watch/listen to and read lectures. This provides a chance to reinforce their understanding and make connections with previous and subsequent lectures.

2. When preparing online lectures, five to six questions related to the content of the lecture must be prepared.

3. There is no need to create a designated time for exams. A set of questions for the exams are prepared from a group of lectures, and students take the exams online. Then the grades will be directly confirmed and entered into the system, where they will be combined and become the results of the semester exam. This has the advantage of making the exam fair and free from interference.

4. The issue of insufficient classroom capacity will disappear, allowing universities to seek alternate, potentially revenue-generating uses for them.

5. Lectures may be given only by the leaders of that major, and, in this way, minimizing the issues of inexperienced young teachers giving lectures and students rejecting or disrespecting their teachers. Young teachers will teach labs, seminars, and practical lessons in the classroom.

6. The quality of teachers will improve, and the requirements for teachers will increase dramatically. Teachers will be highly distinguished for their genuine competence, breadth of knowledge, enrichment of lectures, and use of examples.

7. As the number of teachers decreases, individual teacher salaries will increase.

8. Teachers are to be divided into two groups: (1) those who do lectures (professors with higher degrees) and (2) those who teach labs and seminars (lecturers without degrees). Since they will work together as a team, the concepts of part-time and contract teacher will disappear. The base salary fund will be determined by the total course credits the team teaches. In addition, pay increases will be based on a ranking.

9. There will be a unified laboratory at the entire university and rather than a teaching assistant overseeing the laboratory, an engineer-assistant teacher who is authorized to teach will be in charge.

10. The number of teaching assistants will be reduced.

11. For each major, a team of professors will be formed to work together to provide training on how to teach the courses of that major online and in the classroom.

12. As the classrooms are reduced to a certain level, the teachers' working conditions will improve, allowing them to devote more time to research and self-development.

13. Arrange classroom lessons to be held in the warm season rather than in the winter, allowing schools to save money on electricity and heat. Also, update the study season in accordance with the climate and season.

14. As the procedure for calculating time loads radically changes and is updated and non-prevails, a team of teachers will be established, and collective re-

sponsibility will increase. A team with specific personnel will be responsible for the professional courses. Credit loads will be calculated jointly. Put an end to the issues of overtime pay. The quality of education will improve dramatically, as will teachers' ability to work as a team. Young teachers will experience the benefits of effective teamwork, improving their future skill levels.

15. The credits assigned to the lecturing teacher will not depend on the number of students. As the dependence on the number of students decreases, the transition from quantity to quality will begin, and, in the future, the number of students will decrease drastically, and only a few students with high quality and special learning skills will be admitted to MUST. The ability and quality of MUST graduates will increase, and the country's reputation alongside.

16. The ability to learn from anywhere will create an opportunity for foreign students to enroll. Laboratory courses may be taken at any school laboratory in the student's locale.

17. There will be additional cost savings as classrooms will no longer have to be equipped with expensive technologies.

18. In general, if courses are taught in classrooms in September-October and April-May, there will be huge savings in utilities during the winter season. Students from rural areas will have increased access to education. Student housing costs will decrease. The need for student accommodation will decrease.

19. With the possibility of working from home, teachers will have the opportunity to have side jobs. They will use their own computers, meaning the need to provide teachers with desktop and laptop computers will be reduced. Savings on expenses could contribute to increased salaries. The rank and salary of lecturers will be high. Therefore, those who have not yet earned academic degrees will be motivated to earn academic degrees. Anyone who has not earned their PhD degree within five years will be laid off. This will significantly increase the percentage of teachers with doctoral degrees in the school and increase the possibility of international recognition.

20. As the number of students decreases, this opens the possibility of condensing majors, avoiding the issue of having majors or departments with too narrow focus.

21. The need for paper will be ended by creating an electronic textbook collection. The capacity of the library will increase as the library and all its books will

be electronic. A certain number of approved textbooks should be printed and archived.

22. All kinds of meetings and discussions will be conducted online and there will be no need to equip and maintain large conference rooms.

23. At the level of constituent schools, it will be possible to create joint laboratories between universities.

Conclusions:

1. E-learning has been implemented in the past and is currently being implemented as a necessary step that follows the modern trend of education. The fact that the educational institutions of our country are conducting the training in ways suitable for the level, without interrupting ongoing education as much as possible, is a reason to consider it as appropriate training for the times.

2. In the future, e-learning should be organized based on proper scientific evaluation at the appropriate quality level in accordance with modern trends and requirements, and the basis of clear rules and regulations. It should be officially confirmed as the most important form of education.

3. It is necessary to conduct a proper analysis of the results of e-learning by a wide group of qualified professional professors, scientists, researchers, and teachers with leading degrees and extensive work experience to have a clear understanding of e-learning at the national level.

4. One of the ways to continuously improve the quality of e-learning is to create a unit that conducts research on the improvement of e-learning at certain stages and regularly organize conferences and seminars to share experiences with the work being done in this direction.

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